

Other dyes were prepared by condensing the methiodide with ethoxymethylene or acetanilido methylene derivatives of other ketomethylene compounds².

The higher vinylene homologue of the above dye (Table 1 Compound No. 2) was obtained by the condensation of the desired methiodide (0.4g) with 4-(3-acetanilido-allylidene)-1-phenyl-3-methyl pyrazolone² (0.35g) in absolute ethanol in presence of triethylamine. The compound was isolated in usual manner. m.p.-206° (decomp); yield-25% (Found C, 69.48; H, 4.87; N, 11.53; S, 8.78%. C₄₂H₃₆N₆O₂S₂ requires C, 70.00; H, 5.00; N, 11.67; S, 8.89%). Other dyes of this type were prepared in similar manner using either acetanilido allylidene or methoxy allylidene derivatives of ketomethylene compounds².

The analytical data, m.p.s etc. of all these dyes are described in Table 1.

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Coordination Compounds of Copper(II) Derived from Schiff's bases

(Mrs.) P. R. SHUKLA and (Miss) RENU TAKROO

Chemistry Department, University of Lucknow, Lucknow

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THE use of aromatic Schiff's bases derived from various aldehydes and amines as either anionic monofunctional mono or multidentate or neutral mono or multidentate ligands has attracted the attention

of workers in previous years¹⁻⁴. In the present paper the interaction of aniline and toluidines with benzaldehyde in alcohol has been studied and these Schiff's bases on treatment with copper(II) salts are found to give bright green molecular compounds of 1:1 stoichiometry, whose structures have been determined on the basis of analytical and spectroscopic data.

Discussion

The electronic spectra of complexes contain three sharp bands near 235 nm, 320 nm and 680 nm. The first two of these are also seen in the spectra of free Schiff's bases and the former one corresponds to the perturbed benzene ring transition of the amine fragment and the latter to the whole aromatic molecule oriented *trans* with respect to the double bond^{5,6}. The last one is the characteristic d-d transition of copper(II) in planar environment.

In the i.r. spectra of complexes one broad band appears around 3400 cm⁻¹ which is absent in the spectra of free Schiff's bases. It thus shows that all complexes contain coordinated water^{7,8}. The band at 1600±10 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the azomethine stretch, which in free ligands is observed at 1620±10 cm⁻¹. This small negative shift although an indication of coordination also shows the reduced ability of the Schiff's bases to act as ligands for copper(II), due to steric reasons as already reported⁹⁻¹¹. The phthalate complexes show the asymmetric and symmetric COO⁻ stretches at 1690±10 and 1417±40 cm⁻¹ characteristic of co-ordinated carboxylate ion¹². The molar conductances of these complexes in nitrobenzene are also almost zero, as expected in view of their non electrolytic nature. The sulphate complex on the other hand behaves as 1:1 electrolyte and the ν₃ and ν₄ transitions of uncoordinated sulphate ion are seen at 1120 and 650 cm⁻¹ in the i.r. spectra.

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TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE (IN NITROBENZENE) AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA

Formula	% Cu	% C	% H	% N	Molar conductance in PhNO ₂ in mhos	μ _{eff} in B. M
1. [Cu(H ₂ O) ₂ (C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N)]SO ₄	16.51 (16.10)	39.72 (39.56)	4.52 (4.62)	3.62 (3.55)	20.16	1.886
2. [Cu(H ₂ O)(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N)C ₈ H ₄ O ₄]	15.01 (14.89)	59.43 (59.03)	3.88 (3.98)	3.22 (3.28)	0.18	1.888
3. [Cu(H ₂ O)(o-C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N)C ₈ H ₄ O ₄]	14.50 (14.41)	59.50 (59.90)	4.28 (4.86)	3.21 (3.18)	0.13	1.888
4. [Cu(H ₂ O)(m-C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N)C ₈ H ₄ O ₄]	14.62	59.82	4.72	3.35	0.08	1.884
5. [Cu(H ₂ O)(p-C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N)C ₈ H ₄ O ₄]	14.75	60.02	4.50	3.50	0.07	1.882

obtaining the magnetic and electronic spectral data of the complexes.

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Structural Studies on Palladium(II) and Cobalt(III) Complexes of Isonitroso- β -diketones

B. J. DESAI and V. M. SHINDE*

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University,
Kolhapur-416 004, India.

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ISONITROSOBENZOYLACETONE (HINBA) and isonitrosodibenzoylmethane (HINDBM) have been used in this laboratory for the spectrophotometric determination of iron, palladium and ruthenium¹⁻³. The present communication deals with the preparation and structural characterization of solid complexes of Pd(II) and Co(III) with HINBA and HINDBM.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. HINBA and HINDBM were prepared by the reported methods⁴. Palladium complexes were prepared by mixing acidic solution of PdCl₂ and alcoholic solution of ligand in 1:2 molar ratio. On dropwise addition of sodium acetate orange-red complexes precipitates out. The precipitate was digested on a hot plate for 20-30 min, filtered, washed with water, ethanol and finally dried

under vacuum. Cobalt(III) complexes were prepared by mixing aqueous solution of CoCl₂ and alcoholic solution of ligand in 1:3 molar ratio and then added sodium hydroxide solution to precipitate complexes. Rest procedure is followed as above.

Metal was estimated by standard methods and nitrogen by microanalytical method. Magnetic susceptibility measurement was made by Gouy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as calibrant. IR spectra were recorded on NaCl(KBr) prism using Perkin-Elmer (221) Spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded using Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer and PMR were recorded in CDCl₃ using varian spectrometers with TMS as the standard. The molecular weights of the complexes were determined by cryoscopy method. All the relevant analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The orange-red Pd(INBA)₂ and Pd(INDBM)₂ decompose at 150° and 190° respectively. The yellow-orange Co(INBA)₃ and Co(INDBM)₃ decompose at 210° and 195° respectively. 1:2 and 1:3 stoichiometry for palladium and cobalt complexes respectively were confirmed by elemental analysis and molecular weight determinations. All the complexes are soluble in solvents such as methanol, chloroform, benzene, acetone and ethylacetate. All solid complexes were found to be diamagnetic. This reveals that the palladium complexes must be planar in structure whereas cobalt complexes are octahedral involving d³SP³ hybridization. Bivalent cobalt gets oxidized to trivalent cobalt during complexation with isonitroso compounds.

The PMR spectrum of the HINBA and HINDBM in CDCl₃ show signals at 1.4 and 1.5 τ (with respect to TMS) respectively, which is assigned to the =NOH groups. HINBA exhibits methyl signals at 7.55 τ and phenyl signals at 2.18-2.62 τ . HINDBM exhibits bands at 1.88-2.64 τ . These bands are attributed to proton resonance signals from C₆H₅ groups. The integration of peak areas reveal that the ratio of the area under the peak at 1.5 τ to that under the peak at 1.88-2.64 τ approximates to ten. The metal complexes of both the ligands do not show any signal due to the =NOH group which indicates the replacement of the oxime proton by the metal during complexation.

The IR bands and their characteristic assignment are based on the study of the free ligands and their complexes. The strong and broad band around 3370-3300 cm⁻¹ in ligands is attributed to hydrogen bonded -OH stretching frequency of the oxime group. The disappearance of this band in metal complexes suggests the replacement of the hydrogen of the oxime group by metal on complexation. This observation is in agreement with the results of PMR studies. One strong band at 1660-1650 cm⁻¹ in metal complexes is assigned to C=O of aromatic ketone which indicates that the complexes are symmetric in nature. The weak band at 1620 cm⁻¹ in the ligand is assigned to C=N